

ON THE ROBUSTNESS OF ADAPTIVE PREDICTIVE SCHEME FOR TRACKING RANDOMLY TIME-VARYING CHANNELS

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the use of adaptive predictive algorithms in order to improve tracking performances of classical identification scheme. The performances of coupled structure depend on the prediction device. In this paper, we present a new robust algorithm for the predictive scheme. The robustness deals with insensibility of proposed algorithm to the input statistics variations, namely the power and fourth order statistics. We illustrate our contribution by performances evaluation of the proposed structure in double non stationary context: on tracking random walk channel with speech input signal

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the LMS algorithm is commonly used for stochastic time-varying channels identification ([1][2]). Its steady states performances are analyzed for various situations. It was shown in particular that when dealing with independant random walk variations, the best tracking performances are obtained for white input ([3]). Identification schemes using input pre-whitening filters constitute an alternative to improve tracking capabilities. Different solutions are possible. In this paper, the less complex scheme, depicted in figure (1), is used ([4][5]). The main idea is to use white signal to update the adaptive filter. The input prewhitening process uses an other adaptive algorithm. As previous, the well known LMS algorithm can be used. In this paper, we present a new robust algorithm for the predictive scheme. The robustness deals with insensibility of proposed algorithm to the input statistics variations, namely the power and fourth order statistics. In fact, when the input is non stationary such as speech signal, the robust LMS will overcome the limitations imposed by the LMS algorithm.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the non stationary study context and the adaptive algorithms used for system identification and input prewhitening. In section 3, we propose the Robust LMS

based on second and fourth order statistics. Finally, in section 4, experimental results are presented in order to justify the validity of the proposed algorithm.

2 THE CONTEXT

2.1 Adaptive identification scheme using adaptive input prewhitener

We are interested by system identification. The output of the non stationary channel is given by:

$$y(k) = F(k)^T X(k) + b(k) \quad (1)$$

where $X(k) = [x(k), x(k-1), \dots, x(k-N+1)]^T$ is the speech input observation vector and $b(k)$ is the additive output noise. The time-variations of $F(k)$ are modeled by a random walk:

$$F(k+1) = F(k) + \Omega(k+1) \quad (2)$$

where each component $\omega_i(k)$, $i = 0..N-1$ of $\Omega(k)$ is a zero mean, independent of $x(k)$ and $b(k)$. We note $P_x = E\{x(k)^2\}$, $P_b = E\{b(k)^2\}$ and $P_\omega = E\{\omega_i(k)^2\}$, $\forall i = 0, \dots, N-1$.

2.2 Adaptation algorithms

Two adaptive filters are used: the $H(k)$ is used for system identification and $P(k)$ is used for input prewhitening. The system adaptation algorithm is given by:

$$H(k+1) = H(k) + \mu e(k) X^f(k) \quad (3)$$

where $e(k) = y(k) - H(k)^T X(k)$, and $X^f(k) = [x^f(k), x^f(k-1), \dots, x^f(k-N+1)]^T$ is the observation vector of prewhitner output.

The output $x^f(k)$ of the pre-whitener filter $P(k)$ is the prediction error of the input signal $x(k)$. It is given by:

$$x^f(k) = x(k) - P^T(k) X^\alpha(k) \quad (4)$$

where $X^\alpha(k) = [x(k-1), x(k-2), \dots, x(k-L_P)]^T$, L_P is the predictor taps number.

The pre-whitener filter $P(k) = [p_1(k), p_2(k), \dots, p_{L_P}(k)]^T$ is updated by minimizing the mean square error criterion, and its adaptation is given by:

$$P(k) = P(k-1) + \mu_P g(x_k) x^f(k-1) X^\alpha(k) \quad (5)$$

Where μ_P is the predictor step size and $g(x_k)$ is a normalization factor which characterizes the algorithm. In this paper, two classical algorithm are used and a new one is proposed:

- For the LMS algorithm, $g(x_k)_{LMS} = 1$.
- For the NLMS algorithm $g(x_k)_{NLMS} = \frac{1}{\hat{\sigma}_x^2(k) + \epsilon}$, where $\hat{\sigma}_x^2(k)$ is an estimate of the input power.

For speech signal, it is determinate using the following recurrent relation:

$$\hat{\sigma}_x^2(k+1) = \gamma_1 \hat{\sigma}_x^2(k) + (1 - \gamma_1) x(k)^2 \quad (6)$$

2.3 Classical algorithms limitations

In a previous work [6], we show the sensibility of the LMS and NLMS performances to the input fourth order statistics variations. In fact, for given two sequences with the same power but with different distributions, the NLMS behavior is not the same. Furthermore, since speech signal is non stationary, the power and fourth order statistics are subject to fluctuations. So the NLMS is not appropriate for this case. In the next section, we present a new robust algorithm for the predictive scheme. The robustness deals with insensibility of proposed algorithm to the input statistics variations, namely the power and fourth order statistics.

3 THE RLMS ALGORITHM

3.1 The RLMS idea

To make the adaptive filter robust to the fourth order statistics variations, we propose to modify the normalization factor as follows: $g(x_k) = \frac{\hat{\sigma}_x^2(k)}{\hat{z}_x(k) + \epsilon}$, where $\hat{z}_x(k)$ is an estimate of the 4th order statistics. It is given by:

$$\hat{z}_x(k+1) = \gamma_2 \hat{z}_x(k) + (1 - \gamma_2) x(k)^4 \quad (7)$$

The RLMS algorithm can be described by the following equation:

$$P(k) = P(k-1) + \mu_P \frac{\hat{\sigma}_x^2(k)}{\hat{z}_x(k) + \epsilon} x^f(k-1) X^\alpha(k) \quad (8)$$

3.2 The RLMS robustness analysis

To stress on the robustness of the proposed algorithm, let us consider the prediction case where $L_p = 1$. We assume that the original input signal follows an AR1 model:

$$x(k) = \rho x(k-1) + n(k) \quad (9)$$

where $n(k)$ is i.i.d zero mean signal and $|\rho| < 1$. We measure the performances of predictive part by the mean square deviation $MSD_{pr} = E((p(k) - \rho)^2)$.

For the stationary signal $n(k)$, MSD_{pr} is determined by using independence assumption:

$$MSD_{pr} = \frac{\mu_p \sigma_n^4 [6\rho^2 + (1 - \rho^2)a_n] [\rho^2 + (1 - \rho^2)a_n]}{2\rho - \mu_p \left[\rho^2 + \frac{1 - \rho^4}{6\rho^2 + (1 - \rho^2)a_n} \right]} \quad (10)$$

Where $\sigma_n^2 = E\{n(k)^2\}$ is the power of original noise $n(k)$, and $a_n = \frac{E\{n(k)^4\}}{E\{n(k)^2\}^2}$ measures the flatness of $n(k)$ distribution.

For high correlated input signal ($|\rho|$ close to 1), the MSD_{pr} can be approximated by:

$$MSD_{pr} \approx \frac{6\mu_p \sigma_n^4 \rho^3}{2 - \mu_p \rho} \quad (11)$$

It's important to note that, the performances of the predictive part is not dependent on the 4th order statistics.

In the next section, we will illustrate the performances of the coupled adaptive prediction and system identification for speech input signal and random walk channel variations.

4 PERFORMANCES EVALUATION

4.1 Simulation conditions

We measure the performances of the proposed structure using the Mean Square Deviation (MSD). It is defined as:

$$MSD = \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} E\{(H(k) - F(k))^T (H(k) - F(k))\} \quad (12)$$

To illustrate the performances of the proposed structure, the case of 2 taps channel ($N = 2$) with $P_\omega = 0.005$ and $P_b = 0.1$ is studied. The input signal is a phonetically balanced sentence in french language "Il se garantira du froid avec ce bon capuchon". The sampling frequency is set to 16 kHz and the amplitude signal range is $[-1, 1]$.

4.2 Flatness of MSD versus adaptation step size

The evolution of the MSD versus the normalized step size ν is plotted in figure (2). The schemes studied are classical identification scheme and the 3 predictive schemes piloted by LMS, NLMS and RLMS. We remind that $\nu = \mu N P_x$, for classical scheme, and $\nu = \mu N E(x_k x_k^f)$, for predictive schemes. This figure shows that for small step size, the three schemes are equivalent to the classical scheme. It shows also that in the case of classical scheme, the critical step size leading

to the algorithm divergence is very close to the optimal one. With the proposed scheme they become distant.

It's important to note that the curve of MSD , given by the predictive scheme piloted by RLMS algorithm, is flat. This is very important from the practical view point: an error on the estimation of optimum size doesn't affect the performances of the coupled structure.

4.3 Predictor order influence

Figure (3) illustrates the influence of the predictor order on the tracking performances. This figure show that for small values of L_P ($L_P \leq 5$), the optimal MSD decreases as the predictor order L_P . The improveness is considerable in the in case of the RLMS algorithm. For higher values of L_P , MSD_{min} continue to decrease in case of LMS algorithm but degradates in case of NLMS and RLMS. We can so conclude that the case of 5 taps predictor piloted by the RLMS algorithm leads to better tracking capabilities.

4.4 Ability for input prewhitening

In order to evaluate the ability of input prewhitening of the adaptive predictive algorithm used in the identification scheme, the evolution of the first and second order correlation coefficient of the prewhitened input $x^f(k)$ are plotted. Each correlation coefficient $\rho_i(k)$ is estimated using the classical reccurent relation

$$\rho_i(k) = \frac{\gamma\rho_i(k-1) + (1-\gamma)x(k)x(k-i)}{\hat{\sigma}_x^2(k)} \quad (13)$$

It is important to note that optimal step size μ_P^{opt} is chosen in order to lead to better tracking capabilities (not to lead to better input prewhitening).

Figure (4) illustrates the evolution of $\rho_1(k)$ and figure (5) illustrates the evolution of $\rho_2(k)$. Theses curves are obtained for optimal tracking capabilities in case of a predictor order equal to $L_P = 5$. These figures show that as expected, the best inuput prewhitening is obtained using the RLMS algorithm. The NLMS followed by the LMS are less powerfull but they permit a reduction of the input correlation when compared to the original one (classical identification scheme without prewhitening).

4.5 Ability for input stationarization

We analyse the evolution of the power and fourth order statistics of the identification algorithm input $x^f(k)$. Figure (6) (resp. (7)) illustrates the evolution of the prewhitened input power estimation $\hat{\sigma}_x^2(k)$ (resp. fourth order statistics estimation $\hat{z}_x(k)$). These figures show that as expected the input statistics vary in time. This is due to the non stationary characteristic of speech signal. Therefore, these fluctuations are well reduced when the NLMS and the RLMS algorithms are used.

5 CONCLUSION

In this paper, a solution to improve adaptive predictive identification scheme is presented. A robust algorithm RLMS based on second and fourth order statistics is adopted. When used in double non stationary context (speech input and random walk system variations), it is shown to lead to better tracking capabilities than the classical LMS and NLMS.

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Figure 1: Adaptive identification scheme using a prewhitener at the input of the adaptation

Figure 2: Evolution of MSD versus normalized step size.

Figure 5: Evolution of the second order correlation coefficient.

Figure 3: Predictor length influence on the tracking capabilities: MSD_{min} versus L_p .

Figure 6: Evolution of the prewhitened input power.

Figure 4: Evolution of the first order correlation coefficient.

Figure 7: Evolution of the prewhitened input 4^{th} order statistics $\hat{z}_x$.